

Economic Optimization of PV Array Tilt Angle

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Abstract

Optimal tilt angle of PV array is when the system generates maximum amount of electricity. Such optimum tilt angle for Jerusalem is 25 degrees. This optimum is from the energy point of view.

PV array supplies electricity to energy consumer or to electric utility grid. In case when the related electricity tariffs are according to peak demand, the cost of electricity in peak hours is much higher than in off-peak hours. Therefore it may be expected that the yearly optimum tilt angle from the economic point of view will be declined towards months and hours with the highest electricity tariffs. This would result in lower economic optimum tilt angle than from the energy point of view (25 deg).

The analysis of energy generation and energy cost according to peak demand tariffs shows that for unlimited area available for PV array, the optimum tilt angle from economic point of view is similar to the optimum from the energy point of view (25 deg). This happens because of low sensitivity of energy generation in tilt angle range 0-25 deg in summer, comparing to very high sensitivity in winter, which means that the economic benefit from increasing tilt angle in January is higher

than from decreasing the tilt angle in July in range 0-25 deg. Optimum tilt angle for January in Jerusalem is 52 deg.

This work contains large volume of useful data and may be helpful for other works related to solar energy.

Introduction

Detailed analysis requires solar radiation data for tilt angle with 1 deg resolution for specific location. This information is not available. This work develops methodology for estimation of solar radiation with 1 deg resolution of tilt angle at specific location (Jerusalem).

The estimated solar radiation will be multiplied by peak demand electricity tariffs for each hour. Monthly average day is applied for calculations.

It is considered that unlimited area is available for PV array, therefore unlimited spacing of PV panels rows may be designed with almost zero shading on other rows. Therefore this work does not include consideration of spacing of PV array and relation between tilt angle, spacing, shading, PV array size and electricity generation.

All conditions are for Israel so the results do not necessarily apply to other countries.

Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually metric units apply Joule as energy unit. In this work the energy unit is kWh. 1 kWh equals to 3,600,000 J, 3.6 MJ.

Application of kWh instead of Joule is very convenient for works involving electricity generation and electric tariffs.

All data in this work are for uniform time, without DST, GMT+2 for the whole year. Electricity peak demand tariffs were normalized also to uniform time, GMT+2, for the whole year.

Solar Radiation in Israel

Global Solar Radiation

PV absorbs global solar radiation, which combines both direct radiation and diffused radiation.

The optimal tilt angle for diffused radiation is 0 deg (horizontal array), and the optimal tilt angle for direct radiation is 90° minus the current angle of the sun from horizon.

Sources of Data

Global solar radiation in Israel can be found at the Meteorological Service Internet site [1]. The site details solar radiation for main locations in Israel, hourly results for typical year based on data from years 1991-2005. The results are for horizontal surface.

This work applies data for Bet Dagan, which is near Tel Aviv, and for Jerusalem. The final optimization is done for Jerusalem.

Chart 1 - Global solar radiation in Bet Dagan and Jerusalem on horizontal surface according to [1], [kWh/m²,day]

Other publication of the Meteorological Service details hourly radiation according to tilt angle in Bet Dagan [2]. The results are for every 15° of tilt angle.

This publication is for specific year with very big differences to source [1]. Therefore this source of data [2] will be used only for determination of the ratio of hourly solar radiation between tilt angles. According to this source of data [2] maximum yearly energy in Bet Dagan is received on 30 deg tilt angle.

Dr Sami Suraqi from the National Physical Laboratory conducted research and actual measurements of global solar radiation according to tilt angle in Jerusalem [3]. The results are for every 5° of tilt angle

Chart 2 - Global solar radiation according to tilt angle in Jerusalem [3].
[kWh/m²,year]

According to the above graph optimum tilt angle from the energy point of view is 25° for Jerusalem (latitude 32°).

Procedure for Determination of Global Solar Energy for Any Degree of Tilt Angle

As mentioned before maximum amount of solar energy in Jerusalem is received on tilt angle 25 deg, according to reference [3]. However reference [3] does not include hourly data. The only available publication which includes hourly data for various tilt angles is reference [2]. Reference [2] is for Bet Dagan, with solar radiation slightly different than Jerusalem. The tilt angle resolution in reference [2] is every 15 deg. In addition, reference [2] is for specific year which is very different from long term averages of source [1].

Following procedure will be applied for estimation of solar radiation in Jerusalem for any tilt angle:

- Calculations of ratio of 15 deg to 0 deg tilt angle for Bet Dagan based on reference [2] (ratio 15/0) for every hour
- Correction of ratio 15/0 for all hours, based on daily and yearly symmetry of solar radiation
- Determination of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle 15 deg by multiplication of solar energy in Jerusalem on 0 deg tilt angle based on reference [1] by ratio 15/0
- Linear interpolation of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle in range 0-15 deg
- Calculations of ratio of 30 deg to 15 deg tilt angle for Bet Dagan based on reference [2] (ratio 30/15) for every hour
- Correction of ratio 30/15 for all hours, based on daily and yearly symmetry of solar radiation
- Determination of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle 30 deg by multiplication of solar energy in Jerusalem on 15 deg according to previous calculations based on reference [1] and [2] by ratio 30/15
- Calculations of ratio of 45 deg to 30 deg tilt angle for Bet Dagan based on reference [2] (ratio 45/30) for every hour
- Correction of ratio 45/30 for all hours, based on daily and yearly symmetry of solar radiation
- Determination of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle 45 deg by multiplication of solar energy in Jerusalem on 30 deg according to previous calculations based on reference [1] and [2] by ratio 45/30
- Linear interpolation of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle in range 45-30 deg
- Extrapolation of 45-30 deg line to 25 deg
- Determination of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle 25 deg based on extrapolation of 45-30 deg interpolation line
- Linear interpolation of hourly solar radiation in Jerusalem on tilt angle in range 15-25 deg

Interpolation of Data in Tilt Angle Range 0-15 deg

Information source [2] is for tilt angle with 15° resolutions. The formula for determination of solar radiation on tilt angle is very complex and requires data of cloudiness for every hour. As the cloudiness data for every hour are not available, it is not possible to use the formula.

This work applies linear interpolation between points of available data for 15 deg tilt angle resolution, between each 15 degrees of tilt angle.

Scientifically the approach of linear interpolation is not acceptable. Practically, this approach gives some results which are much better than application of any end of the range (0°, 15°, 30° and so on).

Table 1 - Table Linear interpolation for tilt angle range 0° and 15°

Tilt, deg	Measured [3]	Interpolation	Δ
0	2,054	2,054	
5	2,106	2,093	0.6%
10	2,144	2,133	0.5%
15	2,172	2,172	
$\Delta/15^\circ$		118	
$\Delta/1^\circ$		7.87	

As we can see from the above table, application of linear interpolation results in small error, not bigger than 0.6%, which may be regarded reasonable and acceptable.

Chart 3 - Solar energy curve and linear interpolation in tilt angle range 0-15 deg

As we can see from the above graph, the linear interpolation is always below the measured solar energy, therefore the linear interpolation is conservative (calculated solar energy is underestimated).

Correction of Data

Source [1] includes global radiation data for 0° tilt angle for Bet Dagan and for Jerusalem.

The most problematic source of data is hourly solar radiation according to tilt angle in Bet Dagan [2] because it is related to specific year.

This work does not apply directly the solar radiation data as in source [2]. This source is used for determination of ratio between the solar radiation on higher tilt angle to lower tilt angle (like 30 deg to 15 deg) for every hour.

Generally, monthly results of this ratio should be symmetric with June axis and hourly results should be symmetric with solar noon axis. Solar noon is in Israel at about 11:40 winter time.

Such symmetry based on single year may occur only in summer, on no cloudy days. In other seasons the ratio of direct radiation to diffused radiation is changing with cloudiness influencing the symmetry of data.

To improve somehow the symmetry of data source [2] this work applies averages of symmetric results of the radiation ratio. The example of symmetric data may be May 10:00-11:00 and May 12:00-13:00. May should be symmetric with July, which results in set of four values of the ratio results (like 30°/15° ratio):

- May 10:00-11:00
- May 12:00-13:00
- July 10:00-11:00
- July 12:00-13:00

Calculation Results of Solar Radiation on Tilt Angle in Jerusalem

Following is the graph of solar energy in Jerusalem after data correction as explained above, comparing to reference [3].

Chart 4 - Global solar radiation on tilt angle in Jerusalem [kWh/m²,day]

The difference between both lines may be explained by different ranges of years used in both cases. As the line "Calculated" is based on official data for Israel and is more conservative, this line will be used for further analysis.

Chart 5 - Global solar radiation in Jerusalem for tilt angle 0°, 15°, 30° and 45° according to [1] and [2] [kWh/m²,day]

Tilt Angle Optimization for Maximum Energy

According to [3] maximum yearly energy from solar radiation in Jerusalem (latitude 32°) is for tilt angle 25 degrees.

Tilt Angle Optimization for Telecommunication Devices

Telecommunication devices must work in the worse solar radiation conditions. This happens between 15 December and 7 January.

According to [3] optimum tilt angle in Jerusalem for December is 55°.

Peak Demand Tariffs

Peak demand tariffs in Israel for year 2017 are published in [4].

USD exchange rate on 1 Jan 2017 was 3.86 NIS/\$.

Table 2 - Peak demand tariffs for year 2017, Hi-Voltage [USD/kWh]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Peak	0.22	0.22	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.24	0.24	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.22
Intermediate	0.13	0.13	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.13
Off-peak	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.08

Power of PV Array

The size of PV array is expressed in kWp – kilo-Watt-peak.

This does not mean that 1 kWp will supply 1 kW of electricity when solar radiation is 1 kW.

Determination of various losses related to PV array is very complex and much beyond the scope of this work. This work is for optimization of PV array tilt angle and not for determination of PV electricity generation. In tilt angle range between 0° and 30° the losses for any tilt angle are similar and do not influence the optimization results.

Energy losses related to PV are not calculated in this work but estimated based on some commercial projects as 26%.

Solar radiation on horizontal surface in Jerusalem is 1,981 kWh/y. Theoretically 1 kWp of PV should generate in Jerusalem 1,981 kWh/y. Considering 26% losses, 1 kWp of PV shall generate in Jerusalem 1,464 kWh/y. This value is regarded as "peak hours equivalent" and "Jerusalem has 1,464 hours of PV per year".

For demonstration of economic impact of the optimization, the PV array nominal size applied in this work is 1 MWp (1,000 kWp).

Energy Consumption Profile

It is assumed that all electricity generated by the PV array is consumed by the energy consumer connected to high Voltage electricity grid and paying for the electricity according to peak demand tariffs. For such case energy consumption profile is not required.

Calculations of Income from PV

Formula 1 - Income/saving from PV

$$S \text{ [USD/y]} = P * \sum \{SE(hr_{i,m}) * Eff * T(hr_{i,m})\} \quad (\text{for all solar hours of 1 year})$$

S	income from PV = saving of electricity [USD/y]
P	nominal power of PV array [kWp]
SE(hr _{i,m})	solar radiation in hour i and month m [kWh/m ² ,hr]
Eff	efficiency of the PV system, in this work (100% - 26% losses)
T(hr _{i,m})	electricity tariff for hour i and month m [USD/kWh]

Table 3 - Income from 1 MWp PV array according to tilt angle

Tilt	PV Generation kWh/y	Income USD/y	Δ to Opt USD/y	Income to Opt	Income ¢/kWh
14°	1,536,376	165,922	-2,895	98.28%	10.800
15°	1,541,543	166,388	-2,429	98.56%	10.794
16°	1,544,686	166,631	-2,186	98.70%	10.787
17°	1,547,830	166,874	-1,943	98.85%	10.781
18°	1,550,973	167,117	-1,701	98.99%	10.775
19°	1,554,117	167,360	-1,458	99.14%	10.769
20°	1,557,260	167,603	-1,215	99.28%	10.763
21°	1,560,403	167,846	-972	99.42%	10.757
22°	1,563,547	168,089	-729	99.57%	10.750
23°	1,566,690	168,332	-486	99.71%	10.744
24°	1,569,833	168,575	-243	99.86%	10.738
25°	1,572,977	168,818	0	100.00%	10.732
26°	1,569,268	168,334	-483	99.71%	10.727
27°	1,565,559	167,851	-967	99.43%	10.721
28°	1,561,850	167,368	-1,450	99.14%	10.716
29°	1,558,142	166,885	-1,933	98.85%	10.710
30°	1,554,433	166,401	-2,417	98.57%	10.705

The optimum tilt angle is when the income from PV is maximum. This happens at 25 deg tilt angle.

The optimum tilt angle from the economic point of view is similar to the optimum from the energy point of view, also 25 deg.

Chart 6 - Energy and income for tilt angle

Analysis of the Results

From the energy point of view, the optimal tilt angle of PV array is when the PV array generates maximum amount of electricity. Such optimum tilt angle for Jerusalem is 25 degrees.

From the economic point of view, the optimal tilt angle of PV array is when the income from PV array reaches maximum. Also for maximum income, the optimum tilt angle for Jerusalem is 25 degrees.

Table 4 - Income in January and in July

Tilt	January	Δ	July	Δ
	USD/m	USD/m	USD/m	USD/m
0°	6,913		39,439	
5°	7,440	527	39,334	-105
10°	7,967	527	39,230	-105
15°	8,494	527	39,125	-105
20°	8,962	468	38,690	-434
25°	9,430	468	38,256	-434
30°	9,641	212	37,020	-1,236

Optimum tilt angle for January is 52 deg and for July 0 deg (horizontal array).

In tilt angle range 0-25 deg higher tilt angle gives more profit in January than loss in July. Above 25 deg the situation is changed and income loss in July is much higher than the benefit in January. This is the reason that the optimum tilt angle for maximum income remains to be 25 deg, as for the maximum energy generation.

Constant values of difference to previous result in range 0-15 deg and 15-25 deg are results of linear interpolation of solar radiation for tilt angle.

It would be expected that the economic optimum tilt angle is lower than the energy optimum, because of higher electricity tariffs in summer.

The above analysis shows that the optimum tilt angle from economic point of view is similar to optimum from the energy point of view, 25 deg. This happens because of low sensitivity of energy generation in tilt angle range 0-25 deg in summer, comparing to very high sensitivity in January, which means that in tilt angle range 0-25 deg, the economic benefit from increasing tilt angle in January is higher than from decreasing the tilt angle in July. As this sensitivity is reversed above 25 deg, the optimum tilt angle on yearly basis for Jerusalem is 25 deg, similar to energy optimum, which is maximum yearly solar energy.

References

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